

**SYNTHESIS OF MEDICINES BASED ON THE COORDINATION COMPOUND OF
Zn(II) WITH GLUTARIC AND NICOTINIC ACIDS****Gazieva A.S.
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Chronic deficiency of the trace element zinc is known to lead to immunodeficiency. Zinc is an effective immunostimulant. Zinc is present in all internal organs, tissues, fluids, and almost 100% of the body's enzymatic systems. Zinc acts as a "secondary mediator" of immune cells and significantly shortens the duration of inflammation. When a person catches a cold, a large amount of zinc is consumed in the first few hours, and the need for it increases 6-8 times. Zinc has anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial properties. Zinc reduces susceptibility to acute lower respiratory tract infections. Zinc ions stimulate the production of endogenous α - and γ -interferons, which also exert antiviral activity, including against COVID-19.

Based on the above, a targeted synthesis and study of the physicochemical properties of a mixed-ligand coordination compound of Zn(II) with bioligands—glutaric (GLA) and nicotinic (NA) acids—was conducted.

Zinc nitrate and sodium hydroxide of analytical grade were used in this study. The ligands were glutaric (GLA) and nicotinic (NA) acids of pharmacopoeial grade. The isolated compound was analyzed for metal content using complexometric methods. The melting point of the resulting complex was determined using a TU-25 apparatus. To establish the purity and identity of the obtained complex, X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded using a DRON-2.0 setup with a copper anticathode. IR spectra were recorded using a PERKIN-ELMER FTIR spectrophotometer in the 400-4000 cm^{-1} range. Thermal analysis was performed using a F. Paulik, J. Paulik, and L. Erdey derivatograph (MOM, Hungary).

Synthesis of $\text{Zn}(\text{GLK}-2\text{H})(\text{NK})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 0.006 mol NaOH and 0.006 mol NK were dissolved in 5 ml of water. A solution of 0.006 mol NaOH and 0.006 mol (GLK) in 5 ml of water was added to the sodium salt of NK. When 0.006 mol of an aqueous solution of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was added to the ligand solution, a precipitate formed, which was stirred on a magnetic stirrer for two days. The precipitate was filtered and washed several times with water and ether.

The composition and some physicochemical properties of the synthesized complex compound are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1.

Elemental analysis results for the synthesized complex compound

Compound	Found, %			Calculated, %		
	M	N	H ₂ O	M	N	H ₂ O
$\text{Zn}(\text{GLK}-2\text{H})(\text{NK})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	19,20	4,13	7,96	19,15	4,10	7,91

Table 2.

Some physicochemical properties of the synthesized complex compound

Compound	Color	Mel.poin t, °C	Yield, %	Solubility, g/100g water
$\text{Zn}(\text{GLK}-2\text{H})(\text{NK})\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	White	248	78	insol.

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A new zinc biocomplex was synthesized. IR spectroscopy and thermal analysis revealed that succinic and nicotinic acids coordinate to the metal bidentately in the deprotonated form.